

**MAIN TRENDS IN THE FORMATION OF INTERNATIONAL
EDUCATIONAL HUBS**

Mukumova Nargis Nuriddinovna

Senior Lecturer,

Olimova Lola Erkinovna

Teacher,

Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction,

Abstract: The article describes the essence and development trends of international educational hubs. In response to the demands of globalization, many countries have focused their efforts to implement the policy of creating international and other educational hubs, the processes of transforming their higher education systems, and intensifying their international activities, expansion of joint programs of universities as tools to increase their competitiveness

Key words: educational hub, international integration, Concept for the development of higher education, transformation of universities.

According to the concept of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, one of the main directions for reforming the higher education system is: “transformation of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan into a hub for the implementation of international educational programs in Central Asia.” [1]

In the modern world, acquiring new knowledge is quite in demand. Knowledge is never superfluous, and many are constantly trying to learn something new in their field by attending lectures, courses, various seminars and trainings. For

such people, educational institutions are specially created - hubs, which operate as educational and training centers. Lectures, conferences, educational seminars and master classes are held here. For this purpose, certain spaces are created that have all the necessary conditions and modern equipment designed for productive collaboration. Here anyone can receive any kind of service. The formation of international educational hubs is one of the most striking events in international higher education in recent years.

The creation of an educational hub at the level of an individual state is the result of systematic work to unite the efforts of many local and international participants in the educational sector - universities, students, research centers and specialists in the development of education and the knowledge industry [3].

First of all, it becomes necessary to determine in whose interests educational hubs are formed, what are the prerequisites for their development and what are the principles of their functioning (Figure 1).

Figure 1 allows us to systematically approach the problem of justifying the creation of educational hubs.

Figure 1. Creation of educational hubs

Thus, changes in education, as such, are associated with the need to form a “society of the future”, which must be prepared not only for life, but also for management. Such preparation must begin with the transformation of not only

curricula, but also the approaches to education used.

The hubs host various cultural events, meetings, lectures on various fields of science and life, young specialists gain experience, etc. An educational hub may also include a coworking function. The main task of both institutions is to encourage people to communicate and self-development and to provide the most comfortable conditions for this process. Didier Hoch, CEO of Biovision, says: “We have learned from our experience that a fundamental prerequisite for the success of a hub is the ability to combine technical, administrative and investment knowledge in one place.” [2]

In a narrow sense, an educational hub is a city, country or region where a large number of educational institutions operate, providing high-quality and widely recognized education to both foreign and local students in various fields. And in a broader sense, an educational hub is understood as a certain country designed to attract local and foreign students, attract domestic and foreign investments in the development of the education sector, stimulate the exchange of ideas between individuals and organizations around the world, create a whole complex of educational institutions, companies, scientific- research and technology centers working together to achieve strategic goals - creating cross-border education and building a knowledge-based economy.

However, at present there is already a fairly stable tendency towards the fact that the process of obtaining education is less and less tied to a specific geographical area. This significantly expands the scope of available training programs in various educational institutions of the world, without moving directly to the place where this education is received. This is facilitated by new educational technologies used by educational institutions around the world.

The opportunity to master an educational program remotely becomes an additional incentive to attract foreign students, which ultimately ensures the participation of educational institutions, in particular higher education, in rankings

in order to subsequently occupy top places in them.

In general, the United States is the leader in accepting foreign students. They accept approximately 1 million international students per year. The second place in the world is occupied by Great Britain, the third by Australia.

According to, international student mobility is becoming an important factor influencing the development of the economy of a country or region. In addition, students, in particular foreign ones, are considered as the basis for increasing human capital.

Accordingly, international student mobility includes not only intercontinental, but also regional mobility. Not only educational hubs, but also international agreements such as NAFTA, ASEAN or APEC are aimed at creating the most attractive conditions for students. Note that attractive conditions include such conditions as safety, high quality of education, effective learning outcomes, the offered lifestyle, and reasonable prices.

To ensure the influx of foreign students into the country, states are developing appropriate strategies. By 2025, Australia plans to attract 720 thousand foreign students, Malaysia - 250 thousand foreign students.

In the process of developing such strategies at the state level, it is necessary to take into account which platforms are used by future students when obtaining information about training programs, the admission process, communication.

Thus, the results of the study conducted by Hobsons, showed that 85% of potential foreign students use social networks when deciding which country to go to study; 82.2% of students use social networks to search for information about the higher education institution in question for study - 82.2% of students directly when submitting an application – 41.1% of future students.

The most popular communication platforms among students were Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram. Among the instant messengers is WhatsApp.

Thus, attracting foreign students is becoming one of the trends in the further

development of international educational hubs. The main idea of forming such hubs is that a student can receive a diploma from an international university without leaving their country. As a rule, such hubs are located in large cities or capitals. Today, the main country of presence of international educational hubs is the United States, with a total number of such institutions equal to 78 units. The hubs are mainly located in Boston. The second country in terms of the number of international educational hubs is Great Britain – 39 units, the third is France – 28 units [2].

Thus, among potential foreign students in educational institutions of higher education, there remain those who do not consider a specific country for study, as well as university rankings. This allows educational institutions of higher education in any country with a low rating to attract foreign students, demonstrating the high quality of education

References

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” dated October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847.
2. Studying abroad: opinions of students and parents [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://bilimdinews.kz/?p=6412> - Cap. from the screen.
3. Galichin, V.A. International market of educational services: main characteristics and development trends: Manual / Galichin V.A. - Moscow: Publishing House RANEPА, 2015.
4. Nuriddinovna, M. N., & Zokirovich, S. A. (2022). FEATURES OF WORLD RANKINGS OF UNIVERSITIES. World Bulletin of Management and Law, 10, 95-98.
5. Zakirjanovna, Y. M., Nuriddinovna, M. N., & Qizi, C. B. U. (2022). Higher education in the era of digitalization.

6. Mukumova, N. N., & Olimova, L. E. (2020). Market of Higher Education Services in Uzbekistan. Journal of marketing and Emerging Economics.
7. Мукумова, Н. Н. (2021). Высшее образование в эпоху цифровизации. Наука, техника и образование, (6 (81)), 54-57.
8. Мукумова, Н. Н., & Олимова, Л. Э. (2021). СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО РЫНКА ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ. Вестник науки и образования, (15-1 (118)), 21-24.